

HIGH INTEGRATION OF RESEARCH MONOGRAPHS IN THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable 7.2 Dissemination toolkit

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Dissemination level	:	PU
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DRAFT VERSION

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I. Visual identity

The visual identity of the HIRMEOS project has been developed by UGOE and approved by the consortium. All items of the dissemination toolkit have been uploaded on Google Drive in the following folder:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/0B5tFs6K6DRZ8eU9oQ2RIZUJCCcGc>.

In the folder the partners can find PDF files ready to be printed or disseminated online. Also InDesign files have been made available to the partners who will so be able to customize the products on their requirements. Above all, the posters should be adapted to different audiences. In addition, it is important to update posters and flyers when particular developments of the project so require.

The logo of the project is an idea of the designer Durim Azemi.

All the other items of the Dissemination toolkit, except for the newsletter, have been realized by the designer Katja Töpfer.

A. Logo

A logo displaying project acronym "HIRMEOS" in different formats (eps, jpg, web and print format, pdf, png, svg)

A color scheme defining two primary colors:
 primary color "blue" : 0/92/165, #005CA5
 primary color "yellow": 249/157/62, # F99D3E

Blue

Color (printing)
 CMYK 96/69/4/0
 Color (web)
 RGB 0/92/165
Corporate typeface

Yellow

Color (printing)
 CMYK 0/45/85/0
 Color (web)
 RGB 249/157/6

NexaBold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890!@#%&*

NexaLight

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890!@#\$%^&*

S

Acknowledgement of EU Funding for HIRMEOS

Funded by the Horizon 2020
Framework Programme of the
European Union

B. Template for Presentations

On PowerPoint presentations concerning the HIRMEOS Project must always appear the HIRMEOS Logo, the OPERAS Logo and the EU-HORIZON Logo, like in the template here presented and uploaded on Google Drive:

C. Posters

Two different posters have been prepared, one with more textual information and another with a slogan but less texts. The partner will use the kind of poster which suits best their specific needs.

HIRMEOS
High Integration of Research Monographs
in the European Open Science Infrastructure

Access is fundamental to notable scholarship

OPERAS network HIRMEOS

standards & technologies
DOI, ORCID, FundRef
NERD
DOAB PR Types
Hypothesis
Crossref, Google Scholar
Altmetrics

services
Identification
Entity Recognition
Certification
Annotation
Usage metrics

aggregators
OpenAIRE
DOAB
library catalogues
etc.

platforms
OpenEdition (Lode)
QAPEN (Arno)
Göttingen UP (DSpace)
EKT publishing (OMP)
ubiquity press (OMP)

open science infrastructure EOSC

HIRMEOS Context
HIRMEOS takes place within the larger network OPERAS (open access in the European research area through scholarly communication) that joins more than 20 partners to build up a distributed research infrastructure for the Humanities and Social Sciences. The Project is run by nine European partners committed to innovative scholarly communication and is based upon five Open Access books publishing platforms giving access to more than 8000 scholarly books. HIRMEOS is funded with the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme aiming at user-driven e-infrastructure innovation.

OPERAS
Open Access in the European Research Area through scholarly communication

Funded by the Horizon 2020 Research Programme of the European Union

Stay updated about HIRMEOS activities and subscribe to our newsletter.

www.hirmeos.eu

HIRMEOS PARTNERS
GEORG-ALBERT-FUNDAZIONE GÖTTINGEN
UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO
EKT
DARIAH-EU
OpenBook Publishers
OpenEdition
ubiquity press
Max Weber Stiftung

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HIRMEOS Main Goals

- Integrate Open Access monographs into the open science ecosystem in a systematic and coordinated fashion.
- Prototype innovative services for monographs in support of Open Science infrastructure.
- Provide additional data, links and interactions to the documents.
- Boost user-driven innovation in the academic book publishing sector, both commercial and non-commercial.
- Pave the way to new potential tools for research assessment.

HIRMEOS Services

Common framework

Standard Identifiers: So as to allow cross-linking and facilitate information retrieval, all the platforms will implement identifiers for Documents (DOI), authors (ORCID) and funders (Funder registry).

Certification service: A dedicated service will deliver certificates to the publishers based on their peer-reviewing procedure and the open license used.

Advanced services

Interacting: An online annotation application will allow for scientific exchanges between users and authors.

Discovering: A named entity recognition and disambiguation tool will improve the indexing and facilitate the discovery of new contents.

Measuring: Usage metrics will be standardized on all the platforms and enhanced by adding measures of downloads, citations and alternative metrics.

Stay updated about HIRMEOS activities and subscribe to our new sletter.
www.hirmeos.eu

D. Flyers

Two slightly different flyers have been designed to promote the projects across different kinds of stakeholders. The flyer with the slogan “Access is fundamental for notable scholarship” is specifically intended to present the HIRMEOS project to scholars, academics or research institutions. The flyer with the slogan “Shaping new way to open the book” is more generic and intends to present HIRMEOS to different kind of stakeholders like libraries, publishers and policy makers.

2. Flyer for Libraries, Publishers and other Institutions

What HIRMEOS does

We want to intensify usage on open access books through addition of new services and data. In order to reuse and improve the existing open access publishing platform infrastructure, 5 different publishing platforms for open access books from different countries, of different size and with different technologies have been selected to participate to the project: Open Library (OPEN Foundation, NL), OpenEdition Books (CNRS-CLIO, FR), Ubiquity Press (UK), Gottingen University Press (UGOE, DE), EKT-ePublishing (EKT/NHRF, GR)

- We will increase coordination and cross-linking between the platforms and with other indexing services
- We will integrate research books in the European Open Science Cloud
- We will boost user-driven innovation in the academic book publishing sector, both commercial and non-commercial

Based on the metadata and data that HIRMEOS will bring, the platforms will be able to develop their own innovative services and provide them to the end-users. Therefore, HIRMEOS does not hinder competition between the publishing platforms but grounds it upon a common technological level they all share.

By improving already existing publishing platforms and repositories participating in the OpenAIRE infrastructure, the HIRMEOS project will increase its impact and help including more disciplines into the Open Science paradigm, widening its boundaries towards the Humanities and Social Sciences and to reach out new fields up to now poorly integrated.

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July 2017

Shaping new ways to open the book

HIRMEOS PARTNERS

DARIAH-EU

EKT

OpenBook Publishers

Max Weber Stiftung

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Why HIRMEOS

Not enough has been done yet to integrate Open Access monographs into the open science ecosystem in a systematic and coordinated fashion. That's the main goal of High Integration of Research Monographs in the European Open Science (HIRMEOS) project. The project addresses the particularities of academic monographs as specific support for scientific communication in the Social Sciences and the Humanities and tackles the main obstacles of the full integration of monographs into the European Open Science Cloud. It aims at prototyping innovative services for monographs in support of Open Science infrastructure by providing additional data, links and interrelations to the documents, at the same time paving the way to new potential tools for research assessment, which is still a major challenge in the Humanities and Social Sciences.

HIRMEOS is not a stand-alone project. The project takes place within a larger network, OPERAS – Open access Publication in the European Research Area for Social science and humanities – which brings more than 20 partners from 10 European countries.

HIRMEOS Standards & Services

standards & technologies

DOI, ORCID, FundRef, NERD, DOAB PR types, Hypothesis, Counter, Crossref, Google Scholar, Altmetrics

services

Identification, Entity Recognition, Certification, Annotation, Usage metrics

platforms

OpenEdition (Lodel), OAPEN (Arno), Gottingen UP (DSpace), EKT publishing (OMP), Ubiquity press (OMP)

aggregators

OpenAIRE, DOAB, library catalogues, etc.

Open science infrastructure EOSS

New Datas for new Services

To improve interoperability between the publishing platforms and with referencing and indexing service providers, five sets of data and metadata will be implemented similarly on the platforms.

The data will increase reuse, crosslinking, discoverability, users interaction and trust.

Identification metadata:

- DOI will identify documents (books or chapters)
- ORCID will identify authors
- Funded data will identify funding agencies and research projects linked with the documents

Named Entities data:

- Person names, location and dates will be recognized in the documents

Certification metadata:

- A peer reviewed certificate will be delivered to the documents
- An open license certificate will be delivered to the documents

Annotation data:

- Users annotation will be added to the documents at word level

Metrics metadata:

- Views/Downloads metrics (OAMetrics) will be added to the documents
- Altmetrics will be added to the documents, measuring citations in other publications and social media

RELATED PROJECTS

HIRMEOS PLATFORMS

E. Small Postcard (10 x 7 cm)

Because this small postcard does not contain information which will need to be updated at some point, it represents a practical way to disseminate core ideas and contacts information of the project for its entire duration.

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F. Newsletter

The first issue of the HIRMEOS newsletter was uploaded on the Blog of the HIRMEOS website, www.hirmeos.eu. → <http://www.hirmeos.eu/2017/06/06/hirmeos-newsletter-nr-1-may-2017-is-out/>

A shorter version of the newsletter has been sent to the stakeholders who have subscribed to our mailing list or was disseminated through different social networks.

II. Dissemination level

PU = Public